

Detection of copper(II) and cadmium(II) without cyanide in qualitative analysis[†]

Anupam Chakraborty, Arindam Chakraborty and A. K. Chakravarti*

Department of Chemistry, Dum Dum Motijheel College, 1 Motijheel Avenue, Kolkata-700 074, India

Manuscript received 5 April 2000, revised 13 July 2001, accepted 20 July 2001

In qualitative chemical analysis, in the detection of cadmium(II) when it is present with copper(II) in solution, in order to avoid the use of poisonous and hazardous cyanide and also to overcome the untidy separation of Cu^{II} and Cd^{II} by reduction with metallic zinc or iron, some new methods have been devised, experimentally verified and reported here. Non-poisonous, cheap and common inorganic laboratory reagents are used for the purpose.

Qualitative chemical analysis of metal cations by wet process involves the precipitation method of separation of metal ions in different groups and their subsequent detection by specific reactions. In this, the hydrogen sulfide scheme¹, introduced by Fresenius almost 120 years ago, is still widely practised²⁻⁴, although some other methods (non-sulfidic) have been reported meanwhile⁵⁻¹¹. For the detection of Cd^{II} in presence of Cu^{II} in the ammoniacal solution, the usual method is the complexation of copper

with potassium cyanide solution ($K_{stab} = 2 \times 10^7$) and precipitation of yellow CdS by H₂S. Another method, however, not frequently used, is the reduction of Cu^{II} to metallic copper by zinc (or iron) metal, removal of the solid phase by filtration and passing of H₂S through the filtrate after neutralisation with NH₃ solution.

Apparent inconveniences of the existing methods of detection of Cd^{II} when present with Cu^{II} in solution :

Table 1. Method of detection of Cd^{II} and Cu^{II} together in solution

Sl. no.	Method and procedure	Chemical reactions	Remarks
1.	<p>Thiocyanate solution method :</p> <p>To Solution-I, excess NH₄SCN soln. (~5%) is added, a black slurry is obtained. To it Na₂SO₃ soln. (~5%) is added dropwise with stirring until the precipitate is white. It is warmed, stirred, filtered. The filtrate is boiled with HCl (~1 M) to remove SO₂, neutralized with NH₄OH soln., H₂S is passed yellow CdS appears.</p> <p>Cu^I-thiocyanate is decomposed by HNO₃ and tests for Cu^{II} are performed.</p>	$\text{Cu}^{2+} + \text{Cd}^{2+} + 4 \text{SCN}^- \rightarrow$ $\text{Cu}(\text{SCN})_2 \text{ (black)} + \text{Cd}(\text{SCN})_2$ $2 \text{Cu}(\text{SCN})_2 + \text{SO}_2 + 2 \text{H}_2\text{O} \rightarrow$ $\text{Cu}_2(\text{SCN})_2 + 2 \text{HSCN} + \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$ $\text{Cd}(\text{SCN})_2 + \text{H}_2\text{S} \rightarrow$ $\text{CdS}(\text{yellow}) + 2 \text{HSCN}$	<p>In a mixture of 1 ml Cd^{II} (0.001 M) and 10 ml Cu^{II} (0.1 M), Cd^{II} can be detected</p>
2	<p>Thiosulfate solution method</p> <p>To Solution-II, 2-3 crystals of sodium thiosulfate are added, dissolved by shaking. The blue soln. is decolorized by dil. H₂SO₄, then conc. H₂SO₄ is added to attain 4-6 N, boiled. Red-yellow turbidity becomes black, gets coagulated. It is filtered, the filtrate is neutralized, H₂S is passed - yellow CdS appears. Cu^{II}-sulfide is dissolved in HNO₃ to get Cu^{II}.</p>	$2 \text{Cu}^{2+} + 2 \text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-} + 2 \text{H}_2\text{O} \rightarrow$ $\text{Cu}_2\text{S} + \text{S} + 2\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$ $2 \text{H}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3 + 2 \text{Cu}^{2+} + 2 \text{H}_2\text{O} \rightarrow$ $2 \text{CuS} + 4 \text{H}^+ + 2 \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$ <p>Cd²⁺ remains in solution</p> $\text{Cd}^{2+} + \text{H}_2\text{S} \rightarrow \text{CdS}(\text{yellow}) + 2 \text{H}^+$	<p>A bit longer boiling of the H₂SO₄ soln (4-6 N) is necessary to get CuS formation. 2 drops of Cd^{II} (0.1 M) in 10 ml Cu^{II} (0.1 M) is detectable.</p>

[†]This work is dedicated to Professor S. K. Gupta, Ex-Head, Department of Chemistry, Dum Dum Motijheel College, Kolkata

3. Hydrochloric acid-sulphide method :

To any of the hot solutions of Cu^{II} and Cd^{II} mixture (Solution-I or Solution-II) H_2S is passed till CuS and CdS precipitate completely. The slurry is either filtered and the residue taken up with $\sim 1\text{ M}$ HCl , or directly acidified with HCl to $\sim 1\text{ M}$, boiled for a few minutes, filtered. A few ml of the filtrate is neutralized (NH_4OH) and H_2S is passed—yellow CdS appears.

Residual black CuS is dissolved in HNO_3 and tests for Cu^{II} are performed.

A clean separation and detection is possible. 1 ml Cd^{II} (0.001 M) with 10 ml Cu^{II} (0.1 M) is detectable.

N.B. For detection of Cd^{II} as CdS in the above filtrates, it is better to use a saturated solution of H_2S in water, or a very dilute Na_2S solution in water than to pass H_2S directly from Kipp's apparatus. The method sl. no. 3 is the best.

The cyanide method of masking Cu^{II} in the detection of Cd^{II} in ammoniacal solution is no doubt instructive. However, the reagent cyanide is poisonous and hazardous¹² and hence its use in the practical classes has been prohibited, and in the case with the reduction method, the Cd^{II} in the filtrate cannot be detected confidently by H_2S unless quantitative reduction is attained. Even a trace quantity of Cu^{II} in solution produces black CuS together with yellow CdS .

In order to avoid the existing problems of the above detection processes, the present authors have recommended three methods though the chemical reactions associated therein are well known, which have been verified by repeated experiments and are described in Table 1. The methods are simple and the results are compatible with the existing processes. The methods use cheap, non-toxic common laboratory reagents, and are supported by the work done by the students.

Proposed methods :

Reagents : Stock solutions of Cu^{II} and Cd^{II} , each of $\sim 0.1\text{ M}$, were prepared from $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Merck) and CdSO_4 (dry, L.R., B.D.H.), respectively. Necessary dilutions were made from these stock solutions. All other reagents were prepared from L.R. grade chemicals and approximately of strengths recommended for laboratory use^{2,4}. The following two solutions were prepared.

Solution-I : The mixture of equal or diverse volumes of Cu^{II} and Cd^{II} solutions was treated with dilute NH_3 till turbidity appeared. The slurry was treated with 50% acetic acid solution or 0.1 M HCl .

Solution-II : The mixture of Cu^{II} and Cd^{II} was treated with NH_3 solution till deep blue colour appeared.

Acknowledgement

The authors express their gratefulness to Mr. Anil Chandra Guha, Principal, Dum Dum Motijheel College, Professor H. R. Das, Presidency College, Professor D. C. Mukherjee, Department of Chemistry, University of Calcutta, Dr. M. Chakraborty, Bose Institute, Dr. D. Hait, St. Pauls College, and many veteran teachers of chemistry of different colleges in Kolkata for their interest and encouragement in this work.

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